

On an approximate formula for functionals with respect to stochastic Poisson measure

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The paper constructs a formula for approximate calculation of mathematical functionals by the stochastic Poisson measure. The proposed formula is exact for moments of the third order for the Poisson measure. Examples of using the formula for calculating mathematical expectations for nonlinear functions are constructed.

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1. Introduction

In this paper we consider the issue of constructing an formula for approximate calculation mathematical functionals on a stochastic Poisson measure. The proposed formula is related to the so-called weak approximations. This means that the formula approximates value of some specific functionals, for example, moments, density, characteristic function, etc.

Before moving on to construction of a formula, some definitions and information necessary for the subsequent presentation of the material is need to be mentioned. Here we use the terminology introduced in [1].

Here and below we will assume that some probability space is given $\{\Omega, \mathcal{A}, P\}$ with the filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$, where sample space Ω is the set of all possible outcomes, \mathcal{A} is a σ -algebra on Ω , P is a probability measure and filtration is the family of σ -algebras such, that $\mathcal{F}_s \subset \mathcal{F}_t, s \leq t$ and $\mathcal{F}_t \subset \mathcal{A}$.

We assume that the q -dimensional process $\xi(t) \equiv \xi(t, \omega), \omega \in \Omega$, is adapted to the filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$, which means that $\xi(t)$ is \mathcal{F}_t -measurable for any $t \in [0, T]$. Here for simplicity of notation

the variable ω is omitted.

Let us denote as \mathcal{V}^c the class of random processes $\alpha(t), t \geq 0$ adapted to the filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$, which can be represented as the difference of two monotonically non-decreasing processes whose realizations are continuous with probability 1 for any $t \geq 0$.

Also we denote as LM the class of locally square-integrable martingales, as LM^c — its subclass of stochastically continuous martingales. The function $\langle \mu, \mu \rangle_t = \mathbb{E}[\mu(t)\mu(t)]$, where $\mu(t) \in LM$, is called characteristic of the martingale $\mu(t)$.

A family of martingales $\mu(t, A), t \in [0, T], A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^m)$ is called an orthogonal martingale measure if $\mu(0, A) = 0, \mu(t, A)$ is adapted to the filtration $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ and satisfies the following conditions:

- $\mu(t, A_1) + \mu(t, A_2) = \mu(t, A_1 \cup A_2)$, where $A_1 \cap A_2 = \emptyset$;
- $\mu(t, A_1)\mu(t, A_2) \in LM$;
- $\langle \mu(\cdot, A), \mu(\cdot, A) \rangle_t = \pi(t, A)$, where $\pi(t, A)$ is a random function such that for fixed t it is a measure on $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^m)$, and for fixed A it is a continuous monotonically non-decreasing function of t ; $\pi(t, A)$ is called the characteristic of the measure μ .

Let $\mathcal{L}_0\{[0, T] \times \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^m)\}$ is the class of simple functions that are bounded with probability 1

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on the semiring of sets of the form $(a, b] \times A$, $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^m)$, and H_2^π is a class of random functions $\phi(t, u) \equiv \phi(t, u, \omega)$, such that there is a sequence $\phi_n \in \mathfrak{L}_0\{\mathfrak{S}_0 \times \mathfrak{U}_0\}$ such that exists $P - \lim_{0 \ U} \int \int |\phi(t, u) - \phi_n(t, u)|^2 \pi(dt, du) = 0, t > 0$.

Let E_ξ is a class of twice continuously differentiated functions $f(x)$ and

$$f(t, \xi(t) + \gamma(t, u)) - f(t, \xi(t)) - (\nabla f(t, \xi(t)), \gamma(t, u)),$$

$$|f(t, \xi(t) + \gamma(t, u)) - f(t, \xi(t))|^2$$

and $f(x)$ are integrable on the measure $\pi(dt, du)$ with probability 1.

Here ∇ denotes

$$\nabla f(t, x) = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_q} \right)$$

Now we introduce the concept of a stochastic integral for an arbitrary local martingale and formulate the following theorem (see [1]). This theorem is the Ito's lemma to the case of stochastically discontinuous processes.

Theorem 1. (see [1]) *Let $\alpha \in \mathcal{V}^c$, $\beta \in l\mathcal{M}^c$, μ is a local martingale measure, $\gamma \in H_2^\pi$ $f(t, x)$ $t \in [0, T]$ twice continuously differentiable on x , continuously differentiable on t and $f(t, x) \in E_\xi$.*

Then the process $\eta(t) = f(t, \xi(t))$, where $\xi(t) = \alpha(t) + \beta(t) + \zeta(\gamma, t)$ has a stochastic differential

$$d\eta = d\eta_c + d\eta_d,$$

where

$$d\eta_c = f'_t(t, \xi(t))dt + (\nabla f(t, \xi(t)), d\xi_c) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=1}^q \nabla^i \nabla^j f(t, \xi(t)) d\langle \beta^i, \beta^j \rangle_t,$$

$$d\eta_d = \int_{\mathbb{R}^m} L_d(f, \xi) \pi(dt, du) + \int_{\mathbb{R}^m} f(t, \xi(t) + \gamma(t, u)) - f(t, \xi(t)) \mu(dt, du)$$

and

$$L_d(f, \xi) = f(t, \xi(t) + \gamma(t, u)) - f(t, \xi(t)) - (\nabla f(t, \xi(t)), \gamma(t, u)).$$

The technical aspect of differentiation is significantly complicated. As an example, we can consider the solution of a linear stochastic equation (see [1]):

$$d\eta = \eta d\xi,$$

where

$$\xi(t) = \alpha(t) + \beta(t) + \int_{\mathbb{R}} u \mu(t, du)$$

and $\alpha(t) \in \mathcal{V}^c$, $\beta(t) \in \mathcal{M}^c$, μ is an orthogonal

local martingale measure associated with jumps of a process $\xi(t)$.

The solution has the form:

$$\eta(t) = \eta(0) \exp \left\{ \xi(t) - \frac{1}{2} \langle \beta, \beta \rangle_t \right\} \times$$

$$\prod_{s \leq t} (1 + \delta\xi(s)) e^{-\delta\xi(s)},$$

where $\delta\xi(s) = \xi(s) - \xi(s-)$.

Usually it is impossible to obtain solutions in more general equations in explicit form. Of particular interest are processes that can be

defined as the solution of a stochastic differential equation of the form (for example, in the field of finance):

$$dY(t) = f(t, Y(t-))dt + g(t, Y(t-))dW(t) + \int_{\mathbb{R}} h(t, u, Y(t-))\tilde{\nu}(dt, du), \quad (1.1)$$

where $t \in [0, T]$, $W(t)$ is a Wiener process, functions f , g , h are satisfies to the following

conditions:

- $\exists K_1 > 0: \forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}$

$$|f(t, x) - f(t, y)|^2 + |g(t, x) - g(t, y)|^2 + \int_{\mathbb{R}} |h(t, u, x) - h(t, u, y)|^2 \pi(du) \leq K_2 |x - y|^2,$$

- $\exists K_2 > 0: \forall y \in \mathbb{R}$

$$|f(t, y)|^2 + |g(t, y)|^2 + \int_{\mathbb{R}} |h(t, u, y)|^2 \pi(du) \leq K_2(1 + |y|^2).$$

Here K_1 and K_2 depends on T ; $\tilde{\nu}_t(B) \equiv \tilde{\nu}(t, B)$ is compensated stochastic measure of Poisson, which is associated with $\nu(t, B)$ — stochastic measure of Poisson, which is defined as follows (see [2]):

- for any $t > 0$ $\nu(t, \cdot)$ is a counting measure on $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R} - \{0\})$;
- for a set B , which is bounded below, $\nu(t, B)$ is a process of Poisson with intensity $\lambda = \pi(B) = \mathbb{E}(\nu(1, B))$;
- $\tilde{\nu}$ is a martingale measure and $\tilde{\nu}_t(B) \equiv \tilde{\nu}(t, B) = \nu(t, B) - t\pi(B)$, where B is bounded below.

The solution of such an equation exists in the strong sense and is unique. This means that

exists the unique random process which satisfies to the equation 1.1 (for example, see [2]).

Typically, the Monte Carlo method for simulating random processes is used to calculate mathematical expectations of a solution. However, in the case of processes with jumps, this method is not as effective as for stochastic continuous processes due to the lack of such additional approximations as the Milstein scheme or the stochastic Runge-Kutta method.

This is because the mentioned methods approximate trajectories, but for the Poisson process this is useless, since for this process only the jump times can be modeled. Also a jump is big with respect to time discretization and can't be reduced. As a result, we need to simulate more trajectories to get a reliable result, which means either more power, more time, or more of both.

The issues of approximate calculation of functionals of the solution of equation (1) were proposed earlier, e.g. for the cases were considered when only the diffusion part is present in the equation (when f is zero, see [3, 4]). In the proposed approach the solution of the equation is considered as a functional of the processes on the right-hand side of the equation under the differential sign. Then, it is possible to consider a deterministic equation that can be solved explicitly, in the case of choosing functions convenient for solving the equation that approximate the processes under the differential sign, and the resulting solution is a weak approximation of the solution of the original equation in the sense of approximate calculation of the third-order moments of the solution of the

original stochastic equation. As further studies have shown, it is impossible to construct a solution for the case when there is a drift in the equation, i.e. f is not equal to zero, a non-trivial task, but it can be accomplished if time is considered as a process and approximation is used for it, as was shown for equations with a stochastically continuous part (see [5]). To apply this approach to the case of a process in which there is drift and a stochastically discontinuous part, i.e. $g \equiv 0$, it is necessary to propose another formula.

2. Approximate formula

Let $T = 1$, i.e. $t \in [0, 1]$.

Lemma 1. *The approximate formula $J(G)$ is exact for mathematical expectations of the form $\mathbb{E}[\xi_1 \xi_2 \xi_3]$, where $\xi_j \in \{1, t_1, t_2, t_3, \tilde{\nu}_{s_1}(C_1), \tilde{\nu}_{s_2}(C_2), \tilde{\nu}_{s_3}(C_3)\}$, except $\mathbb{E}[t_1 t_2 t_3] = t_1 t_2 t_3$.*

$$\mathbb{E}G[\cdot, \tilde{\nu}_*(B)] \approx J(G) \equiv J(G, \rho^{(1)}, \rho^{(2)}) = \sum_{j_1, j_2=1}^2 A_{j_1} B_{j_2} \int_{\mathbb{R}} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 G \left[\rho_{j_1 1}^{(1)}(\cdot, u_1) + \rho_{j_1 2}^{(1)}(\cdot, u_2), \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(*, u_3, C, v) \right] \pi(dv) du_1 du_2 du_3 \quad (2.1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{j_1 k}^{(1)} &= a_{j_1 k} I_{[u_k, 1]}(s), \quad k = 1, 2 \quad \rho_{j_2}^{(2)}(s, u_3, C, v) = b_{j_2} I_C(v) I_{[u_3, 1]}(s), \\ I_C(v) &= \begin{cases} 1, & v \in C, \\ 0, & v \notin C, \end{cases} \quad I_{[u_3, 1]}(s) = \begin{cases} 1, & s \in [u_3, 1], \\ 0, & s \notin [u_3, 1], \end{cases} \quad A_1 + A_2 = 1, \\ a_{11} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{-\frac{A_2}{A_1}} \right), \quad a_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{-\frac{A_2}{A_1}} \right), \\ a_{21} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{-\frac{A_1}{A_2}} \right), \quad a_{22} = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{-\frac{A_1}{A_2}} \right), \\ B_1 &= \frac{1}{2\pi(\mathbb{R})} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})}} \right), \quad B_2 = \frac{1}{2\pi(\mathbb{R})} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})}} \right), \\ b_1 &= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})} \right), \quad b_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 + 4\pi(\mathbb{R})} \right). \end{aligned}$$

The moments $\mathbb{E}[\xi_1 \xi_2 \xi_3]$ can be calculated exactly and have the form:

$$\mathbb{E}[t_1] = t_1, \quad \mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nu}_{s_1}(C_1)] = 0,$$

$$\mathbb{E}[t_1 t_2] = t_1 t_2, \quad \mathbb{E}[t_1 \tilde{\nu}_{s_1}(C_1)] = 0,$$

$$\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nu}_{s_1}(C_1) \tilde{\nu}_{s_2}(C_2)] = \pi(C_1 \cap C_2) \min(s_1, s_2),$$

$$\mathbb{E}[t_1 t_2 \tilde{\nu}_{s_1}(C_1)] = 0,$$

$$\mathbb{E}[t_1 \tilde{\nu}_{s_1}(C_1) \tilde{\nu}_{s_2}(C_2)] = t_1 \pi(C_1 \cap C_2) \min(s_1, s_2),$$

$$\mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nu}_{s_1}(C_1) \tilde{\nu}_{s_2}(C_2) \tilde{\nu}_{s_3}(C_3)] =$$

$$\pi(C_1 \cap C_2 \cap C_3) \min(s_1, s_2, s_3).$$

To prove the lemma, it is sufficient to substitute moments into the proposed formula instead of G , where t is replaced by $\rho_{j_1 k}^{(1)} + \rho_{j_1 k}^{(1)}$ and $\tilde{\nu}$ is replaced by the $\rho_{j_2}^{(2)}$.

3. Calculations

Let us look at some examples, demonstrating the usage of the proposed formula.

Let $\pi(\mathbb{R}) = 1$ and $C = \mathbb{R}$, which corresponds to the case of a compensated Poisson process with parameter $\lambda = 1$. Compensated Poisson process we denote as $\tilde{P}(t) = P(t) - t\pi(\mathbb{R})$, where $P(t)$ is a Poisson process with intensity $\lambda = \pi(\mathbb{R})$.

The coefficients $A_1, A_2, a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{21}, a_{22}, B_1, B_2, b_1, b_2$ in the proposed formula can be complex, but in this case, for the convenience of calculations, we will choose them as real:

$$A_1 = \frac{4}{3}, A_2 = -\frac{1}{3}, a_{11} = \frac{1}{4}, a_{12} = \frac{3}{4}, a_{21} = -\frac{1}{2}, a_{22} = \frac{3}{2}, B_1 = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}\right), B_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}\right), b_1 = \frac{1}{2}(1 - \sqrt{5}), b_2 = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \sqrt{5}).$$

Example 1. Let

$$G[t, \tilde{P}(t)] = \sin(\tilde{P}(t)).$$

After substituting this function and the specified parameters into the approximate formula, we obtain approximate value for the $\mathbb{E}[G]$:

$$J(G) = t \left(\cos \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2} \sin \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \left(\cos \frac{1}{2} \sin \frac{\sqrt{5}}{2} \right) \right).$$

Table 1: Results for the functional $\mathbb{E}[\sin(\tilde{P}(t))]$

t	Exact value	Proposed formula	Monte-Carlo method
0.001	-0.000158456	-0.000143197	0.0000103165 0.0000945095 -0.000410649
0.01	-0.00157802	-0.00143197	-0.000101331 -0.00127803 -0.00102422
0.1	-0.01514	-0.0143197	-0.0173112 -0.0129199 -0.0186688

The functional of this type can be calculated exactly, as well as using the Monte Carlo method. From here on, when calculating the results using the Monte Carlo method, we will assume that the number of trajectories used for the approximate value of the functional is not less than 10,000, which is due to the fact that with a smaller number of trajectories, the accuracy of the method drops sharply.

For the Monte Carlo method, the table also provides for each specified time three values, which are obtained by averaging of samples in three different generated bunches of trajectories. We draw the reader's attention to the fluctuations in the calculated values, even with such a large number of trajectories in the beam (10,000 trajectories have been used). The results of the calculations are given in Table 1.

Example 2. Let

$$G[t, \tilde{P}(t)] = \cos(t + \tilde{P}^2(t)).$$

In this case the approximate formula for $\mathbb{E}[G]$ will look like:

$$J(G) = 1 - 0.616548t - 0.818281t^2 + 0.325046t^3.$$

The results of the calculations are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Results for the functional $\mathbb{E}[\cos(t + \tilde{P}^2(t))]$

t	Exact value	Proposed formula	Monte-Carlo method
0.001	0.999540	0.999383	0.999678 0.999632 0.999495
0.01	0.995397	0.993753	0.994804 0.996293 0.994456
0.1	0.950994	0.930487	0.950520 0.948062 0.947834

4. Conclusion

In this paper a formula for the approximate calculation of mathematical expectations from functionals with respect to the stochastic Poisson measure was constructed. It is shown that the formula is exact for moments of the third degree of a stochastic Poisson measure. Examples of using the obtained formula are given. In further studies, this formula will be used to estimate mathematical expectations from the solution of equation (1).

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